

KPI-aware Service Provisioning for Remote Industrial Control Systems Management

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Abstract. The advent of B5G/6G communication infrastructures answers to the requirements posed by emerging use cases and business models, such as Industry 4.0 and autonomous guided vehicles, which impose a set of highly demanding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In this regard, time-engineered applications are of particular importance. Said applications, while do not may impose very demanding latencies, they impose a strict control over them to ensure a deterministic service performance. This has given rise to the concept of Deterministic Networking that relies on adding deterministic capabilities to all involved network infrastructures. In general, optical networks are seen as one of the main enablers of latency and jitter-bounded communications, due to their intrinsic deterministic nature. In the framework of Industry 4.0 use cases, such capability can be exploited to enable remote control of optically interconnected smart factories, contributing this way to reduce both CAPEX and OPEX. However, the estimation of KPIs across optically interconnected smart factories/client domains and the provisioning of end-to-end (E2E) services arises several challenges. In this work, we present firstly multiple service provisioning schemas (single- vs multi-path) leveraging the capabilities of the Software Defined Networking (SDN) paradigm. Then, we provide tools and algorithms for best-case KPI estimation and resource allocation decision and analyze the impact of supporting heterogeneous KPIs into the obtained overall network performance.

Keywords: Deterministic networks, service provisioning, latency, jitter, orchestration, Software Defined Networking, optical networks.

1 Introduction

The jump from 5th Generation (5G) telecommunication infrastructures to the upcoming 6th Generation (6G) is not only driven by the need of supporting higher peak and average data rates, larger coverage and user density, but one of the main goals stems from the need to provide deterministic network performance in multiple fronts, as an answer to the requirements posed by emerging use cases (e.g., connected vehicles, augmented reality, smart factories, etc.). This has given rise to the so-called deterministic communications and networks [1]. In particular, Industry 4.0/5.0 has gained momentum and gathered the interest of both the industrial and research communities [2]. In

such use cases (UCs), industrial assets (e.g., automated vehicles, assembly lines) require a coordinated and time-bounded operation to effectively execute their tasks. To this purpose, the development of network infrastructures with support for network determinism is being key in the recent years.

Nevertheless, network determinism can span multiple facets of the communications, from the supported bit-rate to the experienced communication delays. Among them, there is a special focus on the industry and research community to give support to bounded temporal Key Performance Indicators (KPI), such as latency and jitter [3], particularly significant in the framework of UCs related to the digitalization of manufacturing industries, such as the remote control of smart factories operations. The main characteristic of this type of traffic and applications is that, while related network latencies may not be very stringent, they impose a very strict control over them. This for sure has several implications, ranging from the design of the data plane hardware, the resource allocation strategies and the control/management of both the infrastructure (physical and virtual) and the applications themselves.

Modern applications and network services go beyond pure connectivity resources, also requiring the deployment and execution of specialized functions that allow to materialize the upper level services/applications, such as databases, firewalls, traffic shapers, etc. All these functions require of computational power to be executed. Then, by properly setting up network connections, it becomes possible to inject/extract traffic to/from the functions, in what is known as function chain. However, the execution of said functions at dedicated hardware (i.e., servers) is expensive, both in terms of CAPEX and OPEX.

Following current trends, such as Network Function Virtualization (NFV) [4], these functions are deployed over virtualized resources (e.g., Virtual Machine (VM), container) at commodity servers, which are shared over multiple applications at once, lowering both the infrastructure cost of ownership and operation. For time deterministic services, due to the need of maintaining bounded KPIs (e.g., latencies and jitters), the deployment of the functions usually is done at on premise computational resources or edge sites, close to the communication end-points. Nevertheless, for some range of applications, some functions may be deployed at the cloud, due to not having very stringent deterministic KPIs. This opens the possibility of a better computational resource utilization, at the expenses of more network usage, as well as requiring a finer estimation and control of communication latencies and jitter so as to guarantee the desired service KPIs.

Indeed, the need of monitoring end-to-end (E2E) communication latencies and jitter is of paramount importance for deterministic services with a time engineered performance. However, such parameters are very complex to control and influence, requiring of costly monitoring tools, such as deep packet inspection (DPI) for packet coloring [5], or advanced frameworks for KPI assertion, such as Machine Learning (ML)-aided Digital Twins [6], which require large sets of data and a significant knowledge of the monitored infrastructure, and not forgetting about the high computational power their execution may impose.

Thus, alternative ways for KPI estimation and awareness when provisioning deterministic services is necessary. In this regard, we present first a statistical model for

estimating communication latencies and jitter; a path computation engine (PCE) using said models in order to determine feasible network paths in the context of service provisioning with deterministic KPIs is also presented. The scenario of industrial services in smart factories over optically interconnected network infrastructures is considered. The goal of the engine is to serve as a tool for efficient and sufficiently accurate KPI estimation, opening the possibility to explore alternative service mappings in situations in which computational or network resources may be scarce. Generally speaking, in a multi-domain network scenario, network scarcity may arise depending on the traffic patterns; this is especially true in smart factory networks, since they do have a limited capacity due to costs reasons. However, as will be explained later on, thanks to optical networks technologies, network resources are quite abundant, allowing for materializing the required traffic flows. In this regard, the focus shifts completely to ensure that time-bounded KPIs are met. To this purpose, the developed statistical models and PCE are presented.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the related work to the presented study, especially in the fronts of deterministic networks and related service provisioning; Section 3 details the scenario assumed for the presented work, the related challenges and pursued objectives; Section 4 presents the statistical models for estimating latency and jitter for both deterministic traffic flows, considering the previously described scenario, enclosed in the developed PCE; Section 5 presents some experimental results so as to assert both the performance of the proposed engine and the benefits that KPI awareness introduces in the context of resource mapping decision taking during service provisioning, opening the possibility of alternative provisioning strategies. In addition, by means of an experimental Proof of Concept (PoC), we showcase the operation of the presented solution in practical deployments, while providing a discussion about potential architectural solutions to support the developed engine and its operation; finally, Section 6 draws the main conclusions of the presented work.

2 Related work

The development of a deterministic data plane is crucial in order to materialize time bounded communications. Several efforts have been devoted on the development of advanced wireless infrastructure solutions, such as WiFi 7 or 8 [7], with time performance being one of the core design principles. Similarly, there have been several efforts on providing the means for determinism support at radio access networks (RANs), such as 3GPP domains [8]. They include providing said support at the radio medium and extending it to the wired part, that is, the network that interconnects the several base-band units (BBUs) with the interconnection infrastructure within the domain and beyond. At the same time, the specification of an overall architecture for deterministic networking is being standardized [9], [10], in aims of providing a common framework for definition of involved actors, roles, elements, protocols, and so on.

Parallel to these fronts, there have been significant efforts on the development of control and management solutions for deterministic networks. Following the Software Defined Networking (SDN) framework, authors in [11] propose an SDN-based control for time sensitive networks and discuss the benefits of SDN solutions in the context of industrial and automotive UCs. Indeed, SDN is becoming the de facto standard for the

control plane of deterministic networks, with several works targeting the implementation and validation of full control solutions for the provisioning of communication services with stringent KPIs (e.g., [12]-[14]).

Among the several functions that control and management solutions have to provide, KPI assurance is one of the most important in the context of deterministic communications. First, it requires of adequate monitoring solutions so as to understand the behavior of the underlying physical and virtual infrastructure. Authors in [15] and [16] have provided solutions for monitoring frameworks with a focus on time sensitive communications, which are crucial in the context of industrial applications. The next step relates to the analysis of infrastructure performance and KPI prediction as to understand the expected performance of services to be deployed as well as their effect on existing ones. In this regard, ML-based frameworks have gained interest due to the possibility of inferring network and service properties that otherwise would be difficult to understand employing standard analysis tools (e.g., [2], [17]). However, such tools have the limitations of requiring significant amounts of data for the training of the models, as well as computational power for both training and inference, limiting their use in situations in which data is not reliably available, such as in the context of multi-domain/multi-stakeholder scenarios. Alternatively, the usage of advanced statistical/simulation models becomes attractive (e.g., [18], [19]), due to their lower requirements on available data as well as their lesser computational requirements. Thanks to them, it becomes possible to accurately estimate the achievable KPIs when provisioning deterministic services over a shared infrastructure, including both networking and computing. However, they still require a good understanding of the underlying infrastructure capabilities, with accurately defined metrics so as to model the targeted KPIs in a rigorous way. With such a goal in mind, the current work presents a statistical model for latency and jitter estimation over distributed industrial infrastructures for the materialization of deterministic services. The next section elaborates on the overall considered scenario and the related challenges.

3 Service provisioning in distributed industrial network domains

We consider a scenario in which several smart factories, all of them belonging to the same owner, are distributed over a medium/large-sized geographical area. In order to operate the industrial assets at the distributed premises, a communication network is necessary, thus, each of the industrial infrastructures has its own on-premise network and computing infrastructure, so as to minimize communication latencies and jitters. In order to support deterministic communications, specialized network nodes are employed, with a fine control of the traffic forwarding between input and output ports. In this regard, hardware is usually based on electronic switching, with traffic queues per port in order to properly schedule the traffic. Thanks to several queues, it becomes possible to prioritize the service time of different traffic flows by means of proper queue assignment across all the switches of the selected network path.

Additionally, for the proper execution of operations, several services within the industrial infrastructures may require the execution of specialized functions (e.g., control functions), which also require of computational resources to be executed. In this regard, due to latency reasons, it becomes highly interesting to deploy computational resources

on-site (following edge computing approach), so as to be as close as possible to the communication end-points. In this regard, without loss of generality, we consider that the shared industrial network within a specific factory floor has a shared computational capacity to which each of the network nodes can access and can exploit a specific assigned share, thus, from a modeling perspective, it would be equivalent to have local computational capacities attached to each of the network nodes. This is in line with current developments of computational infrastructures for industrial applications (e.g., [20], [21]), in which a local cloud is implemented to host control applications and related functions. Thanks to the deterministic communications network interconnecting the distributed computational resources, deployed control applications can seamlessly be reached by any network node. Indeed, the combination of deterministic network plus cloud infrastructures tailored to support time-bounded applications and data exchanges provides the backbone for allowing the distribution of software appliances over local or remote facilities [21].

Lastly, the several factory floors are interconnected between them by means of a communication network, so as to allow data exchanges across the distributed infrastructures. In this regard, optical network technologies are seen as enablers for deterministic services due to their guaranteed bandwidth, as well as jitter-free nature (circuits) [22], so in this work is assumed that a circuit-switched Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) optical network interconnects the several client domains (i.e., the smart factory floors). Opto-electronic network nodes act as border nodes between client networks and the optical one, allowing for traffic aggregation at wavelength level. Said optical network is owned by a Network Operator, independent from the smart factory owners, which has full control and ownership over the optical resources. Then, the smart factory owner, by means of contractual agreements, request to exploit the optical network resources in the form of several communication services so as to support the traffic flows between the several factory floors (FFs). Thanks to the abundant optical resources, traffic flows between distributed computational resources across several client domains (i.e., the FFs) can be materialized without capacity bottlenecks, having only the challenge of computational resource allocation and time (latency and jitter) KPI fulfillment (Section 5 provides results in this regard). Figure 1 depicts a schematic of the assumed network scenario.

Fig. 1. Optically interconnected deterministic network domains in support of industrial services.

It is in this scenario in which we consider the deployment of deterministic services as part of the operation of the several smart factory floors, in particular, the deployment of control applications and the communication between them. These control applications, hereafter referred as Virtual Functions (VFs), are characterized by requiring computational power for their deployment (CPU cores, memory and storage), while the communication requirements are stated by a bandwidth and an E2E latency and jitter. For this type of services, a single E2E network path can be configured during the service deployment. Having said that, without loss of generality, we consider services that are structured in the form of two VFs, one representing the front-end of the service/application, such as the dash-board for a system administrator, while the other represents the backend, for instance, the control application for an industrial asset (e.g. assembly line).

Given the service characteristics and the available resources at hand, it is the role of higher control and management planes to determine a suitable layout for both the service VFs onto computational resources, as well as the communications between them into network resources. Due to the deterministic nature of the communications, which impose bounded KPIs, a careful provisioning of services arises of paramount importance, both for fulfilling the service requirements as well as optimizing the usage of the physical resources. Thus, several provisioning strategies may be devised. In this section, we explore the utilization of two provisioning strategies, with the second one being possible thanks to the KPI estimation mechanisms later on presented in this work. Said mechanisms are exploited and implemented by a PCE which, given the posed requirements by connectivity services to be deployed and the status of the physical infrastructure derives the feasible E2E paths.

In this regard, the operation of the PCE would require the support of several control functionalities distributed across the different involved domains. We discuss these details later on in Section 5. Having said that, the next sub-sections detail the strategies proposed in this work in aims of providing KPI-awareness to the provisioning of applications and exploit local and/or computational resources, depending on the application's needs and operational constraints. The operation of the strategies is supported thanks to the PCE, whose details about operation and KPI modelling will be presented in Section 4.

3.1 Local provisioning strategy

As mentioned before, we consider that a control application may be deployed as a set of two VF instances. Ideally, both VFs should be deployed within the computational resources constrained to the origin factory floor infrastructure domain, so as to minimize both latency and jitter communications. In such strategy, hereafter named as Local, the allocation of the VFs is done by balancing the load of the computational resources of the infrastructure, thus, selecting the two least loaded local network nodes in terms of computing resources. More specifically, the Local strategy entails the following steps:

- Starting with the first sub-application at the originating FF infrastructure, find the set of nodes that have enough computational capacity to host the sub-application. As said before, we model the access to computational resources as

having each of the network nodes attached some local computational capabilities to which it has access to.

- Order the set of nodes in ascending order in terms of current load as understood as the average of the individual loads of each of the server resources, that is, number of CPUs, memory and storage. Select the first element of the ordered set as server to be employed for the deployment of the sub-application.
- Repeat the two previous sets of steps for the deployment of the second sub-application, considering the updated status of the computational resources. In this regard, it is imposed that the two VFs are deployed at different resources so as to provide a certain degree of protection against computational resources failures.
 - Once both VFs have a feasible mapping, find the set of candidate paths between the two selected nodes which are compliant with the stated temporal KPIs. To this end, the introduced PCE is employed, which implements several models for KPI estimation, which will be explained in detail in next section 4.
 - From the calculated candidates, select the sub-set that has enough residual capacity at path level in order to satisfy the capacity requirements to support the data flows.
 - Order the set in descending order in terms of normalized path load, understood as the ratio between the residual capacity of the most loaded link in the path and the maximum nominal capacity of the path. Select the first element in the set as network path to materialize the connectivity between end-points.

After this process, the two sub-applications are mapped into resources of the local FF network. An example of a Local allocation is present at Figure 1 (the red-dashed line at the data plane). In case of lack of either computational or networking resources, or that no feasible path compliant with the stated KPIs is found, the service deployment is blocked. The aim of this strategy is to minimize the latency and jitter introduced by the network, keeping the communicating end-points in a close geographical area.

3.2 Remote provisioning strategy

While the usage of local computational costs is beneficial so as to minimize the sources contributing to latency and jitter, thus, having bounded communication KPIs, it may happen that the deployment of all applications and their components requires a substantial amount of computational resources. Thus, in order to keep limited the number of computational resources at the local premises for cost reasons, an interesting alternative allocation schema would be to distribute the two VFs across the multiple client domains, hosting the front-end VF at the origin client domain while hosting the back-end application at some of the other client domains. In this way, it becomes possible to better exploit the distributed computational resources, but only if the KPIs requirements can be kept.

For sure, such strategy, hereafter referred as Remote, requires the usage of extra network resources, especially in the intermediate optical network. Furthermore, and more important, due to network paths being longer, crossing more network elements

(electronic queues, network links, optical switches), the experienced latencies and jitters increase. Nevertheless, its potential enhanced service allocation calls for its consideration. In summary, the Remote strategy consists on the following steps:

- Starting with the first sub-application at the originating FF infrastructure, find the set of nodes that have enough computational capacity to host the sub-application. As said before, we model the access to computational resources as having each of the network nodes attached some local computational capabilities to which it has access to.
- Order the set of nodes in ascending order in terms of current load as understood as the average of the individual loads of each of the server resources, that is, number of CPUs, memory and storage. Select the first element of the ordered set as server to be employed for the deployment of the sub-application.
- For the second sub-application, remove from the candidate list all the nodes belonging to the originating FF. With the resulting set, repeat the previous two steps done to allocate the first sub-application, resulting in the allocation of the second sub-application into remote computational resources in a different FF infrastructure.
- Similar to the Local strategy, once both VFs have a feasible mapping, find the set of candidate paths between the two selected nodes which are compliant with the stated temporal KPIs, employing the same developed engine and models. Note that in this case the resulting path encompasses network resources belonging to different segment, mixing electrical, opto-electronic and optical switches.
- For each one of the calculated paths in the resulting set, split the path into the sub-paths confined to each one of the segments. For each one of them, calculate the residual capacity. For the case of electronic networks, this is done as in the Local strategy. As for the optical segment, this is done by calculating the residual capacity of all continuous wavelength channels from source to destination border nodes. Then, the residual capacity of the full E2E path is the minimum among all the segments.
- Order the set in descending order in terms of normalized path load, understood as the ratio between the residual capacity of the most loaded link in the path and the maximum nominal capacity of the path. Select the first element in the set as network path to materialize the connectivity between end-points. For the sub-path at the optical network, check if there is an already deployed lightpath having enough residual capacity to allocate the new traffic flow. If so, select the lightpath. This can be done thanks to the grooming capabilities at border nodes. In case no existing lightpath is found, determine the continuous wavelength from source to destination and establish a new lightpath with the first available continuous wavelength. We remind the reader that a transparent optical network is assumed.

At the end of the process, the application is deployed, exploiting computational resources belonging to different FFs as well as network resources belonging to both electronic and optical network fabrics. One example of Remote allocation is also present at

Figure 1 (the green-dotted line at the data plane). However, one problem arises in this regard. As said previously, deterministic services impose bounded temporal KPIs, which need to be strictly respected during the allocation of resources. Thus, if no way for measuring or estimating them is present, this alternative allocation strategy (Remote) would not be possible, increasing the blocking of services, unless local computation capabilities are increased, which would come at a cost. As a consequence, it is essential that KPI-awareness and estimation is introduced during the provisioning process, so as to determine the feasibility of the allocations. Said feasibility is determined for sure by the selection of the computational resources' placement and, more importantly, the selection of the network path interconnecting them. Due to the multiple network elements that are traversed, as well as the sharing of network resources between multiple traffic flows, specific paths result in concrete latency and jitter values, which may or may not be compliant with the stated service KPIs. With this in mind, we proposed and developed an engine that implements a KPI estimation tool based on statistical modelling of the latency and jitter experienced by individual traffic flows. Thanks to that, it becomes possible to know beforehand which network paths may result in feasible service allocations, aiding to the overall service mapping process. The next section elaborates on the statistical models developed, considering the multiple network elements involved.

4 Modeling latency and jitter for traffic flows

Before presenting the employed models, let us analyze in more detail the contributors to both latency and jitter of traffic flows, given a selected network path. Figure 2 provides a schematic highlighting the main contributors to these two metrics, considering a service allocation following the Remote strategy. First of all, let us enumerate which are the multiple network elements that packets belonging to a traffic flow need to traverse: 1) the multiple network links between nodes which, for the purpose of this work, are assumed to be fiber links, although only the links at the optical network employ WDM; 2) a set of optical switches; and 3) a set of traffic queues in all the electronic switches and border nodes contained in the network path. Each of the input physical ports of electronic switches has a set of traffic queues, to handle the traffic coming to that node. In addition, several queues are present, with different priorities, so as to classify the traffic according to its characteristics.

Fig. 2. Network elements contributing to latency and jitter of established traffic connections.

According to [23], the latency (or forwarding delay) of a packet in a network is measured by the time interval starting when the last bit of the packet is offered to the input port of the system under test (SUT) (i.e., the E2E network) and ending when the last bit of the packet is received from the output port of the SUT, while the jitter is measured by the absolute value of the difference between the forwarding delay of two consecutive received packets belonging to the same data stream.

Considering said definitions, the latency of a service becomes the sum of all the delays introduced by the several traversed network elements. Starting from the fiber links, they introduce a deterministic delay, which is related to the propagation of the packets through the medium which, in turn, is related to the physical length of the links. Similarly, due to not processing the packets that are being switched over them, the all optical switches also introduce a (quasi-)deterministic delay, which is related to the specific technology and hardware of the optical nodes. The switching delay of optical nodes refers to the time required to traverse the optical node from input to output once the switching matrix has already been configured, that is, the forwarding time at the data plane. This value highly depends on the technology employed (e.g., microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), wavelength grating) and the internal design of the optical node. It is independent of the type required to configure the switching matrix, which is done during the provisioning of the connectivity services by the control/management planes. On the contrary, the delay introduced by the electronic nodes is not constant, but follows a stochastic behavior. Due to the presence of electronic queues, different queueing delays may be experimented at different nodes, depending on the occupancy of the queues, which, in turn depends on the statistical characteristics of the multiple traffic flows supported over them.

Thus, the total latency for a single path (SP) network connection, that is, a connection for which all the traffic follows a single network route, is the sum of all the deterministic delays plus the probabilistic delay introduced by the set of electronic queues. It can be seen how an accurate KPI estimation for both the latency and jitter is of paramount importance since different VF allocations may result in different potential candidate paths, physically speaking, each one of them tied to a specific set of network resources as well as traffic occupancy.

At the same time, some of the services may also require to be very reliable, that is, not affected by network failures that may happen. In this case, the provisioning of alternative multiple paths is required [24], ideally link-disjointed. Indeed, for deterministic networks and services, the purpose of multi path (MP) allocation contributes to the purpose of guaranteeing the desired KPIs. In the case of an MP network connection, the traffic stream is replicated and served over different network routes, each one of them experiencing their own latency and jitter (Figure 2 depicts an example of an MP connection). Thus, it becomes mandatory that both paths are compliant with the service stated KPIs. For example, due to the difference in network delays, it may happen that the same packet arrives at different times at destination through the multiple traffic mirrors that have been provisioned. In such a case, the traffic control and congestion operations may decide to select the packet of the mirror that allows to maintain a steady value for the desired KPIs, discarding the other replicas. Thus, as a consequence, the full packet stream at destination may be composed of packets belonging to different

replicas. As such, in an MP connection, it is also essential to guarantee that the inter-path jitter, that is, the difference in latencies between paths is also compliant with the service KPIs.

With these considerations in mind, we proceed on detailing the modeling for network latency and jitter, this last case considering also the presence of MP. Finally, following current trends, the temporal KPIs of the services also express a probability of assurance, which indicates the degree of satisfaction for the KPIs [25]. That is, due to the probabilistic behavior of several of the network elements, such as traffic queues, it may be not possible to guarantee 100% of the times the KPIs values. This degree of satisfaction then states the bounds, statistically speaking, which must be respected for the KPIs. For example, a probability of 90% would mean that the stated KPIs have to be met in the 90% of the cases. The modelling done starts by considering a simple case of two queues interconnected by an intermediate network with fixed propagation delay, such as an optical network. Once this is done, the model is generalized to consider a broader scenario, in which connections may span multiple electronic-based switches, thus, multiple queues are then considered. This allows us to present the methodology for computing KPIs employing the presented statistical models in any network topology following the aforementioned scenario of optically interconnected deterministic infrastructures.

4.1 Deterministic traffic modeling for two electronic queues

Deterministic networks technology allows for the prioritization of traffic, ensuring data of time-critical applications is given priority over non-time-sensitive data. This prioritization is achieved through traffic scheduling mechanisms such as IEEE 802.1Qbv [26], which enables the transmission of scheduled traffic with exceptionally low latency. Such scheduling mechanisms mold a regular traffic that arrives to a node's buffer following a deterministic behavior.

In Kendall's notation, the model that will characterize this kind of traffic in a node's buffer supporting time deterministic traffic is defined as a D/M/1/k queue [18]. This model defines a queue with 1 server, a deterministic process of arrivals of clients (packets), and a memoryless process of departures. The maximum number of packets in the queue is k, which corresponds to the size of the queue. In this model, arrivals occur at a deterministic rate β , moving the process from state i to state $i+1$, whereas departures occur at a rate μ following an exponential distribution, with an average service time of $1/\mu$ (see Figure 3). If a packet arrives to the system in state n it will suffer a delay of the average service time for each packet in the queue and itself, so the total delay in terms of the state of the queue can be expressed as:

$$t_{queue} = \frac{1 + n}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. D/M/1/k queuing model for deterministic traffic.

Once the queuing model has been defined, one can obtain its stability equations, which define the relationship between the probabilities of each state. As the D/M/1 queue model has already been defined in the literature, it can serve as standing ground to obtain the equations for the equivalent case with a finite number of queue states k . The D/M/1 model defines:

$$P_n = (1 - \delta)\delta^n = P_0\delta^n \quad (2)$$

where δ is the root of $\delta = e^{-\mu\beta(1-\delta)}$ with the smallest absolute value and characterizes the proportion of channel utilization. From here one can easily extract the state probability distribution for the finite k states case by applying some basic properties:

$$\sum_{n=0}^k P_n = \sum_{n=0}^k P_0\delta^n = 1 \rightarrow P_0 = \frac{1}{\sum_{n=0}^k \delta^n} = \frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \delta^{k+1}} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the state probability distribution of a D/M/1/k queue is:

$$P_n = \begin{cases} \delta^n \frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \delta^{k+1}} & 0 \leq n \leq k \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} = \delta^n \frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \delta^{k+1}} \cdot \Pi\left(\frac{n}{k} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (4)$$

The previous model serves to estimate the state of a single electronic queue, which, once determined, allows to derive the probability density function (PDF) of the latency of packets over said queue. In the following, we extend the model so as to consider the presence of two electronic queues, specifically, the ones belonging to two border nodes, which then are interconnected by means of the intermediate optical network. In this case, both the source and the destination nodes contain a buffer that introduces delay due to packet queuing. These queues have been already characterized, so the next step is to define the probability distribution of the delay for the entire path between source and destination. The delay is defined as:

$$t_D = t_{2\text{queues}} + l = \frac{2 + n}{\mu} + l \quad (5)$$

where n is the total number of packets waiting in queue considering the two buffers and l is the deterministic latency of the path between source and destination, that is, the delay introduced by both the fiber links and the optical switches. Therefore, before characterizing the delay distribution of a path, one must compute the distribution of n , the number of packets in queue considering the joint occupancy of both buffers. For example, $n=3$ in this case represents that a total number of 3 packets is being held together considering both queues, the distribution of which may depend on the current

situation (3 in the first queue and 0 on the second, 2 in the first queue and 1 on the second, and so on). Assuming that the statistical distribution of both queues is independent or weakly correlated, the distribution of n is obtained by the convolution of the state probabilities of each queue:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{p_{2q}}[n] &= (f_{p_{1q}} * f_{p_{1q}})[n] = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} f_{p_{1q}}[i] \cdot f_{p_{1q}}[n-i] = \\
 &\sum_{i=0}^k \delta^i \frac{1-\delta}{1-\delta^{k+1}} \Pi\left(\frac{i}{k} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \delta^{n-i} \frac{1-\delta}{1-\delta^{k+1}} \Pi\left(\frac{n-1}{k} - \frac{1}{2}\right) = \\
 &\delta^n \left(\frac{1-\delta}{1-\delta^{k+1}}\right)^2 (k+1) \cdot \Lambda\left(\frac{n+1}{k+1} - 1\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

With the PDF of the states of both queues together and the expression of the path delay, a simple variable change suffices to extract the PDF of the path delay:

$$n = \mu(t_D - l) - 2 \tag{7}$$

$$f_{p_{2q}}[t_D] = \delta^{\mu(t_D-l)} \left(\frac{1-\delta}{\delta - \delta^{k+2}}\right)^2 (k+1) \cdot \Lambda\left(\frac{\mu(t_D-l)-1}{k+1} - 1\right) \tag{8}$$

This expression completely characterizes the probability of a delay t_D . If one wants to compute the probability of a delay lower than t_D , all probabilities from $f_{p_{2q}}[0]$ to $f_{p_{2q}}[t_D]$ are to be added up.

$$f_{p_{2q}}[t \leq t_D] = \sum_{i=0}^{t_D} \delta^{\mu(t-l)} \left(\frac{1-\delta}{\delta - \delta^{k+2}}\right)^2 (k+1) \cdot \Lambda\left(\frac{\mu(t-l)-1}{k+1} - 1\right) \tag{9}$$

Having modelled the delay (latency) considering the presence of two electronic queues interconnected by means of a deterministic network segment, we can proceed on modelling the jitter experienced by packets of the same traffic flow. As explained previously, the jitter is defined as the absolute difference of delays of two consecutive packets (i.e., t_{D1} and t_{D2}), so in this scenario where the latency of a path between source and destination nodes is deterministic only the queues in these nodes will play a part in the distribution of the jitter:

$$J = |t_{D1} - t_{D2}| = \left| \frac{n_1 + 2}{\mu} + l - \frac{n_2 + 2}{\mu} - l \right| = \left| \frac{n_1 - n_2}{\mu} \right| = \frac{\Delta n}{\mu} \tag{10}$$

Therefore, the jitter's PDF will follow the distribution of $J = |t_{D1} - t_{D2}|$ or, what is the same, the distribution of $\Delta n = |n_1 - n_2|$, that is, the absolute difference of queue states. For the case with two queues, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
f_j[\Delta n] &= \begin{cases} \sum_{i=0}^{2k} f_{2q}[i] * f_{2q}[i - \Delta n] & \Delta n = 0 \\ 2 \sum_{i=D}^{2k} f_{2q}[i] * f_{2q}[i - \Delta n] & 0 < \Delta n \leq 2k \end{cases} = \\
&= \begin{cases} \left(\frac{1-\delta}{1-\delta^{k+1}}\right)^4 G_1(0, k) & \Delta n = 0 \\ 2 \left(\frac{1-\delta}{1-\delta^{k+1}}\right)^4 \delta^{-D} G_1(\Delta n, k) & 0 < \Delta n \leq k \\ 2 \left(\frac{1-\delta}{1-\delta^{k+1}}\right)^4 \delta^{-D} G_2(\Delta n, k) & k < \Delta n \leq 2k \end{cases} \quad (11)
\end{aligned}$$

where:

$$G_1(\Delta n, k) = \frac{1}{(\delta^2 - 1)^3} \left[\begin{aligned} &(2k - 2\Delta n)\delta^{2k+2\Delta n+2} + (-2k + 2\Delta n - 4)\delta^{2k+2\Delta n+4} + \\ &(2k - 2\Delta n + 4)\delta^{2k+2} + (2\Delta n - 2k)\delta^{2k+4} \\ &+(1 - \Delta n)\delta^{4k+4} + (1 + \Delta n)\delta^{4k+6} \\ &+(\Delta n - 1)\delta^{2\Delta n+2} + (-\Delta n - 1)\delta^{2n} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (12)$$

$$G_2(\Delta n, k) = \frac{1}{(\delta^2 - 1)^3} \left[\begin{aligned} &(2k - \Delta n + 3)\delta^{2\Delta n+2} + (-2k + \Delta n - 1)\delta^{2\Delta n} \\ &+(2k - \Delta n + 1)\delta^{4k+4} + (2k - \Delta n + 1)\delta^{4k+6} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (13)$$

To obtain the same distribution in terms of the jitter J instead of the difference of queue state, one must just consider the variable change: $J = \frac{\Delta n}{\mu}$. Once again, if one wants to compute the probability of a jitter lower than J , all probabilities from $f_j[0]$ to $f_j[J]$ are to be added up.

$$f_j[j \leq J] = f_j[\Delta n \leq \mu J] = \sum_{i=0}^{\mu J} f_j[i] \quad (14)$$

The previous modelling for both the latency and jitter serves to estimate the KPIs of an SP connection given a stated probability of satisfaction, also allowing to estimate the KPIs of individual paths in an MP connection allocation. Still, the inter-path jitter (for the MP case) needs to be modelled so as to guarantee that the service KPIs are respected as a whole. For simplicity, we consider the case in which only two different network paths are employed. The multipath jitter in this scenario can be computed as the absolute difference of latencies across path 1 (t_1) and path 2 (t_2).

$$J_m = |t_1 - t_2| = \left| \frac{n_1 + 2}{\mu} + l_1 - \frac{n_2 + 2}{\mu} - l_2 \right| = \left| \frac{n_1 - n_2}{\mu} + \Delta l \right| \quad (15)$$

The difference in path deterministic latencies (i.e, Δl) greatly complicates the expression of the probability distribution, and it will vary depending on the value of Δl .

To understand how the distribution is affected by this difference, let us portray it without the absolute value. Variables J_m' and J' represent MP and SP jitter without absolute value respectively, and can therefore be negative:

$$f_{J'} \left[J_m' = \frac{\Delta n}{\mu} + \Delta l \right] = f_{J'} [J' + \Delta l] = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{other} \\ \Pi_1 [J' + \Delta l] & \frac{-k}{\mu} - \Delta l \leq J' \leq \frac{k}{\mu} - \Delta l \\ \Pi_2 [J' + \Delta l] & \frac{-2k}{\mu} - \Delta l \leq J' \leq \frac{-k}{\mu} - \Delta l, \quad \frac{k}{\mu} - \Delta l \leq J' \leq \frac{2k}{\mu} - \Delta l \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where:

$$\Pi_1 [J + \Delta l] = \left(\frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \delta^{k+1}} \right)^4 \delta^{-(J+\Delta l)\mu} G_1((J + \Delta l)\mu, k) \quad (17)$$

$$\Pi_2 [J + \Delta l] = \left(\frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \delta^{k+1}} \right)^4 \delta^{-(J+\Delta l)\mu} G_2((J + \Delta l)\mu, k) \quad (18)$$

From this point, one can obtain the distribution of the MP jitter by applying the absolute value to the results just obtained:

$$f_m \left[J_m = \left| \frac{\Delta n}{\mu} + \Delta l \right| \right] = \begin{cases} f_{J'} [\Delta l] & J = 0 \\ f_{J'} [J + \Delta l] + f_{J'} [-J + \Delta l] & 0 < J \leq \frac{2k}{\mu} + \Delta l \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Thus, the multipath jitter for a couple of electronic nodes interconnected by optic services is fully defined by this expression.

4.2 Deterministic traffic modeling for a generic M queues path

Admittedly, the expressions extracted in the previous sub-section do not apply to most scenarios where path computation for deterministic services is required, as they are only useful for KPI estimation of paths consisting in two electronic nodes, interconnected by means of intermediate network resources. They could be useful for a scenario consisting of two client domain border nodes separated by an optical network domain, for example, but cannot characterize KPIs for entire deterministic client domains. Moreover, they consider equal traffic load for both nodes. Thus, the expressions must be generalized to describe KPIs for paths with any number M of queues, each with different traffic loads. On the other hand, developing the 2-queue limited expressions facilitates the understanding of the queues' probability models and the required extensions to obtain KPI estimations from them, simplifying the development of a generic KPI estimation model.

The first step to estimate path performances is to obtain each node's state PDF, following the same expression in (4), considering the specific traffic arrival and service time of the queue. Once the PDFs of each queue's state in the path is known, a general PDF of the state of the whole path can be extracted by a process of M convolutions, being M the number of electronic switches involved in the path:

$$f_{path}[n] = f_{p_1} * f_{p_2} * f_{p_3} * \dots * f_{p_M} \quad (20)$$

The state of a path can be interpreted as how many service times a packet will have to wait in buffers along the path, so the result of this operation provides valuable information about the delay introduced by electronic buffers. Therefore, it is possible to derive from $f_{path}[n]$ a probability distribution that characterizes the latency of the path, $f_{path}[t]$.

The latency of a path will consist of its deterministic delay l introduced by propagation times and optical switches, added to the non-deterministic delay introduced by the queues. Overall, the latency of the path is defined as:

$$t = \frac{n + M}{\mu} + l \quad (21)$$

which allows for the variable change:

$$f_{path}[t] = f_{path}[n = \lfloor \mu(t - l) - M \rfloor] \quad (22)$$

Thus, the probability of a path latency smaller than τ will be characterized by the cumulative sum:

$$P[t \leq \tau] = P[n \leq \lfloor \mu(\tau - l) - M \rfloor] \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \mu(\tau - l) - M \rfloor} f_{path}[i] \quad (23)$$

From this expression one finds the value of τ that verifies $P[t < \tau] > P$, which characterizes the maximum latency of a path with a probability of P . Note that this is only valid for the cases in which $\lfloor \mu(\tau - l) - M \rfloor \geq 0$, otherwise, $P[t \leq \tau]$ is equal to 0.

In order to extract a path's jitter PDF, one must manipulate its latency PDF to reflect the distribution of the absolute differences in latencies, as per the definition of jitter previously explained. The required manipulation is a convolution of a difference distribution, modified to apply the absolute value, just as described in the two nodes case. For a generic case, the jitter PDF expression will be described with the help of the equation below, in which n_1 and n_2 are the number of packets in the system (i.e., the path) experienced by two consecutive packets of the same flow, similar to the cases explained previously in this section:

$$f_{jitter}[D = |n_1 - n_2|] = \begin{cases} 2 \cdot \sum_{i=D}^{\text{len}(f_{path})-1} f_{path}[i] * f_{path}[i - D] & D > 0 \\ \sum_{i=0}^{\text{len}(f_{path})-1} f_{path}[i] * f_{path}[i - D] & D = 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where, $\text{len}(f_{path})$ refers to the size of the state vector (i.e., the PDF). Once again, this expression defines the probability distribution of all plausible state differences between two consecutive packets. To obtain the distribution that characterizes the jitter KPI, that

is to say, the one which represents the probability of a path jitter under a threshold J , this function must undergo a cumulative sum.

$$P[j \leq J] = P[D \leq J\mu] = \sum_{i=0}^{J\mu} f_{jitter}[i] \quad (25)$$

This way the maximum path jitter within a probability P is computed through a cumulative sum algorithm, which halts when P is reached and returns the value of J .

Finally, as previously pointed out, there are certain types of services that require the allocation of multiple paths, preferably disjoint, to ensure reliability against link failures. Since packets may be arriving from multiple alternative paths, the estimation of MP jitter is essential, in order to discriminate path pairs based on their ability to conform to the stipulated KPIs.

MP jitter follows a similar probability distribution as regular jitter, as it is also defined by the absolute value of the difference in latencies: $j_m = \left| \frac{n_2 - n_1}{\mu} + l_2 - l_1 \right|$. However, the difference in the deterministic delays of both paths, coupled with the inequality of electronic nodes, give a more complex formulation for the estimation of this kind of jitter. Thus, the PDF of the MP jitter for a pair of disjoint E2E paths is computed through the displaced convolution:

$$f_{mp}[j] = \sum_{i=0}^{length(f_{p1})-1} f_{p1}[i] * f_{p2}[i + \Delta l - j] + \sum_{i=0}^{length(f_{p2})-1} f_{p2}[i] * f_{p1}[i - \Delta l - j] \quad (26)$$

where Δl is the difference in deterministic delays between paths 1 and 2, as already detailed in the previous section.

The previous model capable of estimating path KPIs for deterministic traffic enables the implementation of a PCE that performs KPI estimation by computing the necessary convolutions with PDF of each queue's state along a path. The engine processes computation requests that specify the source and destination nodes, the state of traffic in the node queues, the characteristics of the traffic under study (such as packet arrival rate), the desired KPIs, and the required probability of meeting those KPIs. Using this information, the engine identifies potential paths between the nodes that meet the KPI requirements, accounting for a target number of alternative paths if multipath (MP) allocation is requested. Not only feasible paths are calculated, but the estimated KPIs for each path or path pair are also returned. This informed KPI-based path computation facilitates the previously mentioned remote allocation for deterministic services by providing KPI estimates that help eliminate VFs placements and path selections that would otherwise fail to meet service requirements.

At this point, we would like to highlight that while for the sake of the discussion and the results evaluation done in the following Section 5 the well-known Markov model D/M/1/k has been employed, the model for determining the E2E latency and jitter presented does not rely in any predefined statistical model. In fact, it can be seen that it operates with a generic PDF, allowing the PCE to derive conclusions with any available statistical distribution. This is a very powerful result, since it does not constraint the

presented solution to a unique statistical model but rather to any model representing the underlying behavior of both the traffic and hardware elements, namely the queues.

In realistic deployments, with rich monitoring capabilities, it could be possible given empirical measures of the experienced KPIs to derive a statistical model of the traffic at the network level. Said model then could be fed to the PCE, which then would operate with it to derive the desired KPIs (latency and jitter). Furthermore, in order to deal with uncertainty and do periodic adjustments to the obtained statistical models, DT platforms may be exploited, as pointed out during the introduction of the work. However, DT usually rely in advanced ML models to derive their insights, which requires large amounts of data as well as reserved computational power for both the training and the inference, not forgetting about model retuning so as to keep with any deviation experienced due to intrinsic or extrinsic perturbations. All in all, this substantially increases the CAPEX and OPEX of the KPI-aware provisioning mechanisms. On the contrary, the proposed PCE only needs to rely on minimal status information in order to operate, which alleviates substantially the complexity of the overall system.

Let us mention, however, that the main shortcoming for this approach is the reduced adaptability to statistical changes, or uncertainty due to unplanned events. In this regard, one interesting solution would be to employ the presented PCE and statistical models for best-case KPI estimation to then employ some sort of refinement model (e.g., with ML) to confirm the estimation. The necessary ML model in this regard could potentially require less data, since is already relying on the insights provided by the designed PCE. Such solution would combine both the fast and less complex estimation of KPIs for immediate decisions with the long-term outputs of ML frameworks for system refinement and re-evaluation. The design, implementation and operation of such a system is out of the scope of the presented work and left for further studies.

5 Experimental evaluation and discussion

The development of the described PCE and its introduction in the control and management layers of network infrastructures, opens up the possibility to employ alternative service allocation strategies in the aims of enhancing the acceptance of services, given the limited set of distributed computational and network resources. Thus, in this section, we evaluate the advantages provided by having an informed PCE considering the presence of deterministic temporal KPIs. To this end, we consider the situation in which services arrive to the infrastructure following exponentially distributed inter-arrival times and holding times, with mean value HT and IAT, respectively. As explained before, a service is characterized by requesting the allocation of two VFs, which need to be allocated at computational resources and then interconnected between them so as to allow the data exchanges across the functions. We consider that VFs can be characterized in terms of requested computational resources as requiring a set of CPU cores as well as an amount of memory and storage. Having said that, for the results presented in this section, we consider that VFs request between 1-2 CPUs, 128-256 MB of memory and 100-200 GB of storage. As for the connection between them, we consider that the required bit-rate is in the range of 10-50 Mb/s. Considering these resource requirements, services need to be deployed over a shared multi-domain infrastructure. Figure 4 depicts a schematic of the two network scenarios that have been employed, with all

network link distances stated in kms. The size of the electronic queues is assumed to be 10, with four queues per input port of the electronic nodes, one usable for best effort traffic and the resting 3 potentially assignable for deterministic traffic. The propagation delay of the links is considered to be $4.67 \mu\text{s}/\text{km}$ and the switching delay of optical nodes is 1 ms. Moreover, we consider that all links operate at a 10 Gb/s rate, with WDM links having 40 wavelength channels each, which corresponds to half of the standard C band, and a packet size of 1500 bytes for the data flows. Finally, we assume that all nodes at the client network segments (i.e., the smart factory floors) have access to attached computational capabilities equal to 10 CPUs, 4 GB of memory and 4 TB of storage each.

Fig. 4. Topologies of the network scenarios for the experimental evaluation: network 1 (top) and network 2 (bottom).

With such conditions, we focus on analyzing, for various strategies, the acceptance rate of deterministic services. In this regard, in order to analyze the influence of service profile and the potential benefits that KPI-enabled service provisioning opens up, we consider several profiles in terms of required E2E latency, jitter and if reliability is required (thus, MP connections have to be provisioned) or not. Table 1 summarizes the assumed values, which are inspired by the values found at [2]. In addition of the KPIs, the profiles are also characterized by a value named KPI_{prob} , which indicates the percentage in which the stated latency and jitter values should be guaranteed, that is, the probability of satisfaction that we explained in previous sections.

Table 1. Summary of KPI profiles.

Profile name	Latency (ms)	Jitter (ms)	MP required	KPI _{prob} (%)
P1	20	0.5	No	70
P2	5	0.5	No	90
P3	20	0.5	Yes	70
P4	5	0.5	Yes	90

Having said that, firstly we focus on network scenario 1, and measure the acceptance rate of services for increasing values of HT/IAT. We simulated 10^5 service arrivals per data point, considering that services originate in an even share among all client domains. For the first set of results, we focus on profiles P1 and P2, that is, no MP service allocation is employed. The following Figure 5 (left) depicts the obtained results, considering the cases in which only local computational sites can be exploited (Local) and another in which, thanks to the presented methodology, it is possible to compute KPI-bounded paths, thus, allocating VFs to another island if necessary (Remote).

Fig. 5. Service acceptance rate as a function of HT/IAT for network scenario 1 and SP service allocation (left) and MP service allocation (right).

It can be appreciated how the performance of both profiles, although having different latency requirements, yield to almost identical results when considering a Local allocation strategy. This is because, within client domains, due to their reduced size, the length of the physical links nor the number of electronic queues is a constraint, but the main bottleneck arises from the lack of computational resources. Hence, the need of devise a strategy that allows for a better exploitation of the distributed computational resources across all client domain. Thus, the Remote strategy is employed. The materialization of such a strategy only becomes possible if tools for estimating beforehand the feasibility of network paths in regards of temporal KPI compliance is present. Thanks to that the latency and jitter of candidate network paths can be derived, according to the current load at electronic queues, the characteristics of the service to be provisioned as well as the physical characteristics of the network path in between end-points of the service. Note that, depending on the desired KPIs and the network status, it may be possible that no feasible network path is found, thus, services would be blocked not by the lack of computational resources but due to the impossibility to assure

the latency and jitter of the communications. Having said that, we can observe that thanks to being able to estimate with precision worse case KPIs, it becomes possible to assure the performance of deterministic services and exploit all the distributed computational resources, reducing the rejection of services due to lack of local resources by around a 60% for loads yielding acceptance rates greater than 95% for P1. On the contrary, for P2, although some reduction is experienced, this is limited to around 15% in the best case. The reasons behind said differences are that, for P1, the cause of blocking is still exclusively the lack of computational resources, while for P2, around 30%-55% of the blocking is due to KPI unfulfillment, due to its more stringent latency and probability of satisfaction, reducing substantially the benefits of exploiting remote computational resources. This highlights that an accurate KPI estimation is of paramount importance in order to decide if alternative allocation strategies can be applied or not depending on the service characteristics. Let us mention at this point that, for the targeted working points and scenarios presented in this work, the blocking due to the lack of network capacity is nonexistent, since both the intra-FF networks as well as the WDM network have abundant resources to support all traffic flows. This accurately reflects the scenario in which a careful network planning and related investment for its deployment has been made, so as to have an E2E network infrastructure able to withstand the predicted traffic.

To continue our study, we also analyzed the behavior of both strategies considering the requirement of MP allocation, for which profiles P3 and P4 are employed. In such cases, the KPI assurance is much more difficult, since KPIs have to be assured both at individual path level (latency and jitter) as well as inter-path level (jitter), thus, a Remote allocation strategy may be less adequate in such cases. Figure 5 (right) depicts the obtained results.

As before, the Local strategy performs very similarly for both profiles, thus only a curve is represented. It can be seen that for bounded services, but without stringent latency values (P3), even with the added difficulty of MP, it becomes possible to satisfactorily find network paths that interconnect the remote islands if necessary, enhancing the service acceptance. Indeed, similar benefits to the SP case are observed (around 60% reductions in blocking). On the contrary, for profile P4, the benefits are very slim (only around a 4% of reductions is experienced), since a significant portion of the services cannot be fulfilled due to the impossibility of founding multiple network paths that satisfy at the same time the stated KPIs. In such cases, in which both stringent KPIs plus network path diversity is required, it would be better to employ Local allocation strategies, as it would yield to similar results without the need to use extra network resources, which then could be employed for other classes of traffic.

Such results evidence that the network topology and size have a significant influence on the feasibility of finding network paths compliant with stated KPIs. It may happen that, depending on the targeted network infrastructure, the benefits introduced by KPI estimation, which allow for the explained Remote allocation strategy, are lower. Hence, it becomes essential to analyze the impact of the network to the potential blocking probability (BP) reductions. To this end, network scenario 2 is employed, and the same simulations as in network scenario 1 are repeated. Figure 6 below depicts the obtained results for both SP allocation (left) and MP allocation (right). In this regard, we decided

to depict two of the working points and compare the performance obtained for the two network scenarios, comparing them, so as to understand the impact of network topology. In this regard, since the Local allocation strategy will not exploit the intermediate optical network segment, and only exploit the local client network segment, the obtained results for both network scenarios are the same, hence, we depict only the case for Remote allocation.

Fig. 6. Comparison of BP for Remote strategy allocation between network scenario 1 and 2 for SP (left) and MP (right) services.

It can be seen how the BP of services increases notoriously when a wider network is considered, especially in the case of MP services (more than one order of magnitude). This is mainly due two reasons: on one hand, longer fiber paths are employed, which introduce larger propagation delays, while on the other, and more importantly, more optical switches are traversed, fact that increases substantially the added delay due to switching times. These together have as a consequence that the number of services that cannot be allocated due to temporal KPI unfulfillment increases in a large portion, negating the benefits that a Remote allocation brings. In fact, for network 2, the reduction of BP when comparing Local against Remote is less than 1%, indicating that, for such network and service profiles, a Remote allocation strategy is not adequate. Nevertheless, such benefit analysis of alternative allocation strategies becomes possible thanks to the presented KPI estimation-based engine, which allows network operators to tune their allocation and traffic engineering strategies in an informed way.

5.1 Path computation engine scalability performance

Next, in this subsection we analyze the scalability of the proposed KPI estimation model and associated engine. The provisioning time of new services is one of the main performance metrics for which control and management layers are held accountable, hence, if the proposed engine is to be used in realistic deployments, an understanding of its execution time and how it may vary is necessary. With that goal in mind, several tests have been carried out considering a fixed KPI profile P3, to include MP capabilities' effect into the scalability performance tests, and to isolate all variables under study. These variables of interest will be the network's extension and the size of the electronic node's queues. Specifically, for the modification of each one of these control variables a sequence of 300 executions is carried out to extract relevant results.

To study the scalability of the engine’s path computation time against network extension, scenarios network 1 and network 2 have been put head to head. Figure 7 (left) displays the results organized into two cumulative density functions (CDFs). In the case of the network 1 scenario, the execution time is lower than 0.352 s with a probability of 80%, whilst larger network 2 scenario yields to an execution time lower than 0.418 s, for the same probability.

Fig. 7. CDF of PCE’s execution time for network 1 and 2 (left); PCE execution time as a function of queue size for both networks 1 and 2 (right).

These results evidence that the execution time of the engine is dependent on the size and mesh degree of the network, since more alternative paths have to be explored, with the need to determine the KPIs for all of them. Interestingly, we can see that the execution time of network 2 is only 18.75% larger than that of network 1, having the more extensive topology almost 36% more nodes, indicating that a mostly linear proportional increase in execution time is experienced if the network is expanded and more domains are considered. Next, the impact of the size of electronic buffers (queues) is analyzed. Figure 7 (right) depicts the obtained results for both networks considering increasing values of the size of queues (k).

For both scenarios the increase in time appears to follow a linear behavior, where the overall execution time increases less than 40 ms for every buffer position added to the electronic nodes. Overall, both tests have proven the strong scalability of the engine, as increasing the network’s size and complexity does not inflate computation times to unmanageable levels. Indeed, the experienced execution times for the considered scenarios are at sub-second level, making them completely compatible with average service provisioning times in typical network infrastructures.

5.2 Proof of Concept for KPI-aware path computation

To conclude our study, as well as to provide a more complete and balanced evaluation of the presented models and PCE, in this sub-section we present an experimental evaluation in a small-scale testbed scenario, with real hardware implementing both the deterministic network capabilities at the FFs as well as the WDM optical network interconnecting them. The goal of the PoC is to showcase the operation of the PCE in a real network scenario, while elaborating on potential architectural constraints and entities

required. The following Figure 8 depicts a schematic of the PoC, its logical components and how they are related to the various employed hardware equipment.

Fig. 8. Diagram of the implemented PoC for KPI-aware path computation and connection deployment.

The PoC replicates a scenario in which two FFs are interconnected by means of an intermediate optical network. Then, on top of the built scenario, petitions for path computation and network provisioning are made. We decided to focus the PoC in the networking aspect of the overall scenario given that the main contribution of the presented work relates to the PCE for KPI-aware network path computation.

Before proceeding on discussing the details of the PoC and its several components, at this point let us elaborate on the control and management functionalities that the adoption of the proposed PCE would entail in a practical deployment. In this regard, Figure 8 depicts a simplified schematic of a generic control and management architecture to enable the configuration and operation of a multi-domain network scenario, as the one targeted in this work. Generally speaking, such type of architecture would serve the purpose of resource configuration and service provisioning in a broader scenario, giving service to a plethora of coexisting vertical industries. Then, the targeted smart FF UC would exploit the control and management functionalities in place.

The architecture of the control/management layers follows the design principles of the SDN and service-based frameworks, providing several atomic and independent logical modules which collaborate to achieve the KPI-informed deployment of applications and related network connectivity, such as the work presented in [27]. Each of the network segments can be understood as an independent administrative domain; this also applies to the several smart FFs which, although having the same owner, they are independent infrastructures which require their own set of functionalities to operate. Having said that, the several resources, either computational (FFs) or networking (FFs and network fabrics) require some entity that configures them in accordance to upper level requirements. This is responsibility of the multiple SDN controllers at the multiple segments (SDN-FF controller and SDN-optical network controller), which, taking the details posed by higher level requests, transforms them into low level hardware configurations. To do so, at the southbound it may implement several interfaces which can

directly interact with the underlying physical hardware or to intermediate control platforms. These are the logical entities that finally give to fruition to the results derived by the PCE.

Speaking of the PCE, it also requires information about the capabilities, status and topology of the underlying physical network. Thus, the several SDN controllers may also expose the required information. Given the multi-domain nature of the scenario, the information exposed captures macroscopic information, hiding sensitive information regarding the exact nature of the resources or fine-grain details about their capabilities. All this information is collected by the Provisioning Manager at the E2E control and management level in order to compose a full picture of the underlying physical infrastructure. This logical entity is the one responsible for handling petitions for service/application deployments. In this regard, the Provisioning Manager may receive provisioning requests thanks to rich interfaces. Given the requirements of the requests, as well as the infrastructure status information, it contacts the PCE during the calculation of the feasible E2E network paths, in order to have candidates that are compliant with the stated KPIs. Note that the role of the PCE is to compute feasible paths and their associated KPIs, given the status of the E2E network and the requirements posed by new traffic flows, while the logic to decide which are the appropriate resources, both computational and networking, lays on the Provisioning Manager, which for the work presented in this paper would be the strategies described in Section 3. All in all, this architecture represents a potential solution that may be adopted so as to integrate the designed PCE and the formulated statistical models. As pointed out, one of the main challenges in its adoption lays on the information exposure and operations enforcement. To this end, declarative approaches, exploiting the capabilities of SDN, which separates the data from the control plane, would yield to feasible implementations. Then, the challenges lay on the design and implementation of both path computation strategies and provisioning logics.

Having said that, let us discuss in more details the several components of the PoC. Figure 8 (right) showcases the several hardware elements employed to construct the targeted scenario. In the case of the FFs, a single switch with deterministic capabilities is employed for each one of them. More specifically, the employed hardware is a White Rabbit Z16 (WR-Z16) switch [28], which is an Ethernet-based electronic switch with high accuracy timing capabilities for scheduled and deterministic traffic. As for the optical network, an Ixia Network Emulator is employed [29], which enables the construction of interconnecting network fabrics, such as the one depicted in the schematic. Finally, a rackable server executes instances of all control and management entities, including the presented PCE.

Given this hardware, the PoC consists on a provisioning request for a deterministic connectivity services with time bounded KPIs, such as the one required to interconnect computational resources deployed in remote facilities, as it has been explained along the paper. To this end, the previously introduced control/management architecture is leveraged. More specifically, a homebrew Provisioning Manager is present, which accepts provisioning requests via a developed REST application programming interface (API). Upon reception, the Provisioning Manager contacts the PCE, also via a REST

interface in order to request for the calculation of feasible paths given the KPIs stated at the request.

In order to do these calculations, as said before, the PCE requires a set of information. From an architectural perspective, this would be the role of the SDN controllers. In the case of the PoC, said information is obtained via a mix of static parameters from configuration files, such as the topology, nominal network capacity and queue size, and dynamic status information coming from queries to the network equipment via REST interfaces. The several network nodes (the WR-Z16 and Ixia) have an SDN agent that allows for the communication for both exposing status information and receiving configuration orders from/by external control entities. With all these elements, in the following we present the result of a provisioning operation for deterministic network services, highlighting the main interactions and results across all involved entities. Figure 9 depicts the main interactions through relevant Wireshark captures.

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
16.895689...	ClientReq	ProvMgr	HTTP/JSON	1354	POST /e2eservice/pathrequest HTTP/1.1, JS
17.095377...	ProvMgr	ClientReq	HTTP	268	HTTP/1.1 200 (text/plain) (a)
17.478487...	ProvMgr	PCE	HTTP/JSON	71	POST /E2E_KPIEvaluation HTTP/1.1, JSON (a)
17.487819...	PCE	ProvMgr	HTTP/JSON	151	HTTP/1.1 200 OK, JSON (application/json) (b)

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
17.627681...	ProvMgr	CNC	HTTP/JSON	68	POST /v1/net-config/vlan HTTP/1.1, JSON (c)
17.788977...	CNC	ProvMgr	HTTP/JSON	258	HTTP/1.1 202 Accepted, JSON (application/
17.800836...	ProvMgr	CNC	HTTP/JSON	68	POST /v1/net-config/tas/rule HTTP/1.1, JS
17.830643...	CNC	ProvMgr	HTTP/JSON	108	HTTP/1.1 200 OK, JSON (application/json)


```

..{"service_id":
  "13331", "kpis"
  : {"throughput":
    200.0, "jitter":
    : 1.0, "delay":
    50.0}}

```

```

..{"addr": "1c697
A63E036", "vlan_i
d": 3, "vlan_prio"
: 2, "filter_en": 0
, "mac_addr": "ABC
DEF00001", "prot
o": 0, "ip": 0, "vla
n_id_cfg": 0, "por
t": 0, "vlan_prio_
cfg": 0, "dscp": 0,
"dest": 0, "has_de
st": 0, "d_s": 0, "re
dundant": 0, "red_
dest": 0, "red_han
dle": 0, "id": 20}

```

```

..{"interva
l_time": 593682, "gate_
cfg": 8, "id": 3}

```

Fig. 9. Workflow for KPI-aware path computation and connectivity provisioning.

First, an external request for establishing a network connectivity service arrives at the Provisioning Manager via its northbound REST interface (step a). This proceeds on treating the request so as to understand which are the required KPIs as well as the endpoints that need to be interconnected. Once the requirements are known, it contacts the PCE, requesting to obtain a set of candidate paths compliant with the required KPIs. In this request, information about the desired KPIs as well as the status of the infrastructure and its capabilities is passed (step b). With this information, the PCE proceeds on executing the KPI estimation models and path computation algorithms based on that. As a result, the set of feasible paths, with the estimated E2E KPIs achievable through them is obtained. This is highlighted in the text bubble of step b. Then, with the obtained information, the Provisioning Manager proceeds on executing the logic for deciding which is the path that is going to be employed, following the steps explained during Section 3. Finally, given the chosen path, the Provisioning Manager proceeds on requesting the configuration of the underlying physical equipment. Given the scope of the paper, in here we focus on reporting the configuration of the deterministic network equipment, that is, the WR-Z16 switches in the PoC. In this regard, the Provisioning manager contacts the SDN-FF controller (CNC entity in the Wireshark captures) for enforcing the desired configuration (Step c). The configuration can be summarized in

mainly two items: the configuration of a VLAN, for routing and priority setting, and the configuration of Time-Aware Shaping rules [30], which are the responsible for the low-level scheduling of traffic packets. Once all these configurations are done, the connectivity service is finally deployed, all in all, following the selected path compliant with the stated KPIs estimated thanks to the presence of the developed PCE. The presented PoC not only showcased a real operation and implementation of the proposed solution but also elaborated on practical deployment considerations, pointing to architectural requirements and challenges of the studied UC.

6 Conclusions

KPI assurance is of paramount importance during service provisioning. This is especially critical for deterministic services with bounded KPIs. One set of KPIs that is more difficult to control and enforce refers to the temporal characteristics of traffic flows associated to the services, namely, end-to-end latencies and jitter. As such, it becomes primordial to provide frameworks that allow for their accurate monitoring and estimation. This does not only allow for a health control of established traffic flows but also opens the door to alternative service provisioning strategies which, in the absence of tools that accurately estimate the expected KPIs, would not be possible as the risk of KPI unfulfillment may be unknown. In this work, we presented an engine which, employing advanced statistical analysis, it provides latency and jitter estimations for deterministic traffic in a multi-domain network, encompassing both deterministic and optical network segments. Through extensive simulations, we have showcased how an informed KPI route selection allows to explore alternative service provisioning strategies, potentially exploiting resources at far away neighboring domains. Thanks to that, service acceptance can be greatly enhanced (up to 60% reductions in service blocking). In addition, we have analyzed thoroughly which elements, both related to the service profile and the network scenario, make the adoption of alternative strategies, powered by KPI estimation, an interesting alternative, both in terms of obtained increased performance benefit and provisioning time.

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